

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity by filter paper disc technique¹⁰ using a species of gram-positive bacteria, *i.e.* *S. albus* and *B. subtilis* and a species of gram-negative bacteria, *i.e.* *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris*. None of the compounds was found to possess any significant activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes using a sulphuric-acid-bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, 60 MHz pmr spectra in TFA on a Varian spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH-7 instrument at 70 eV. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

The substituted-acetoacetanilides^{11,12} and ethyl-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylate¹³ were prepared according to the procedures reported in the literature.

2-Methyl-N-aryl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxamides (3): (a) A mixture of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1; 0.1 mol) and appropriate acetoacetanilide (2; 0.1 mol) was refluxed in methanol (25 ml) in the presence of a catalytic amount of piperidine for 4 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured into crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from methanol (Table 1). (b) A mixture of ethyl-2-methyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylate (4; 0.1 mol), aniline (0.01 mol) and pyridine (5 drops) in xylene (20 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. After the reaction, xylene was removed and the residual mass cooled. The separated solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol.

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Synthesis of the Anhydrosulphide of Alkylxanthic Acid

R. R. DARJI and A. SHAH*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

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FORMATION of anhydrosulphide of ethyl xanthic acid were reported¹⁻³ through the reaction of potassium ethyl xanthate and ethyl chloroformate. Xanthic acid disulphides on treatment with KCN were reported⁴ to give anhydrosulphides. Simmons *et al.*⁵ have also reported the preparation of anhydrosulphide of ethylxanthic acid by the reaction of tetracyanodithiin with potassium-ethyl-xanthate. The direct formation of anhydrosulphides from the xanthate reaction was observed by Willcox⁶, during the reaction of potassium ethyl xanthate and ether solution of acetyl chloride at room temperature. We now report the formation of anhydrosulphide of alkylxanthic acids (5) from the reaction of sym. phthaloyl dichloride (1) and excess of potassium-O-alkyl-xanthates at room temperature.

The probable mechanism for the formation of anhydrosulphide (5) involves the intervention of unsymmetrical phthaloyl dixanthates (2)⁷, which is supported by reactions of the latter with potassium-O-alkyl-xanthates (Scheme 1) to obtain the corresponding anhydrosulphides (5a-c). We have also isolated thiophthalic anhydride (4) from the above reaction mixture. However our attempt to isolate thiophthalic anhydride (3) from the reaction mixture was not successful which showed that thiophthalic anhydride (3) rapidly changes to thiophthalic anhydride⁸ (4).

Experimental

Reaction of sym. phthaloyl dichloride (1) with excess of potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate: Compound 5a: Phthaloyl dichloride (2.03 g, 0.01 mol) was taken in acetone (50 ml). To this, potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate (6.96 g, 0.04 mol) was added below 0° and stirring was continued for 30 min at 0° and further 30 min at room temperature. Evaporation of solvent after removal of unreacted potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate yielded thiophthalic anhydride⁸ (1 g, 61%), m.p. 110° (m.m.p.) and anhydrosulphide of isopropyl xanthic acid (5a; 1.4 g, 59%), m.p. 52-4° (lit. 54°)⁴, (Found: C, 39.44; H, 5.50. C₈H₁₄O₂S₂, calcd. for: C, 40.33;

Scheme 1

H, 5.88%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 (ϵ 13 630), 258 (ϵ 11 150), 303 (ϵ 15 490), 357 (ϵ 178) and 412 nm (ϵ 161).

Similarly, **5b** and **5c** were prepared in 42 and 65% yield, respectively: compound **5b** (Found: C, 44.65; H, 6.97. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ calcd. for: C, 45.11; H, 6.70%); $[\eta]_D^{25}$, 1.547; λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 (ϵ 12 750), 250 (ϵ 12 750), 303 (ϵ 16 350), 357 (ϵ 222) and 412 nm (ϵ 176); compound **5c** (Found: C, 49.80; H, 7.63. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ calcd. for: C, 49.00; H, 7.40%); $[\eta]_D^{25}$, 1.544; λ_{max} (EtOH) 220 (ϵ , 13 001), 250 (ϵ 12 370), 298 (ϵ 14 920), 357 (ϵ 171) and 412 nm (ϵ 121).

Reaction of unsym. phthaloyl dixanthates (2) with potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate: Compound **5a**: An acetone solution (40 ml) of *O,O'*-diisopropyl-*S,S'*-phthaloyl-dixanthate (2 g, 0.005 mol) was treated with potassium-*O*-isopropyl-xanthate (0.87 g, 0.005 mol) at room temperature for 30 min. Evaporation of the solvent after removal of unreacted potassium-*O*-isopropyl-xanthate yielded thiophthalic anhydride⁹ (0.4 g, 49%), m.p. 110° (m m.p.) and anhydrosulphide of isopropyl xanthic acid (**5a**; 0.9 g, 76%), m.p. 52–4° (lit. 54°)⁴.

Similarly, **5b** and **5c** were synthesised in 75 and 81% yield, respectively.

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Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-II. Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some New 2-Substituted-amino-5-(2,4- dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and -thiadiazoles†

M. M. DUTTA, B. N. GOSWAMI and J. C. S. KATAKY*

Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006

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SEVERAL 1,3,4-oxadiazole and -thiadiazole derivatives have been widely reported to exhibit bacteriostatic^{1,2}, hypoglycemic^{3,4}, diuretic⁵, muscle relaxant^{6,7}, analgesic⁸, insecticidal¹, herbicidal^{8,9} and antifungal^{10,11} properties. Keeping this in view, some new 2-substituted-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4a–g**) and -thiadiazoles (**5a–h**) were synthesised from the corresponding 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl)-4-arylthiosemicarbazides (**3a–h**) by oxidation with iodine in potassium iodide and cyclodehydration with phosphoric acid, respectively, and screened for fungicidal activities against two fungi, *Curvularia verruciformis* and *Alternaria tenuis*. The newly synthesised compounds were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectroscopic data. The schematic presentation of the reaction sequences are given in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Buchii oil heated apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Parkin—Elmer 237B spectrophotometer using potassium bromide discs. Pmr spectra were determined in solutions stated, with tetramethylsilane as the internal reference and recorded in 60 MHz on a Varian T-60 spectrometer.

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